

${}^6A_{1g} \rightleftharpoons {}^2T_{2g}$ spin-crossover in iron(III) dithiocarbamates

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Literature on ${}^6A_{1g} \rightleftharpoons {}^2T_{2g}$ spin-crossover in iron(III) dithiocarbamates for the last three decades has been reviewed, and kinetics and mechanism of spin-crossover in these systems have been discussed.

Introduction

Iron(III) dithiocarbamates are the first example¹ of spin-state equilibrium systems in transition metal complexes. Iron(III) dithiocarbamates have also the distinction of having been studied most exhaustively employing a battery of physicochemical techniques, viz., magnetic susceptibility measurements, Mössbauer, EPR, NMR, UV-VIS and IR spectroscopy, X-ray crystallography and laser Raman T-jump, kinetics method. The subject was last reviewed by Martin and White² in 1968. During the three decades, there has been commendable progress towards understanding the kinetics and mechanism of the spin-crossover transformation in iron(III) dithiocarbamates. Hence, this review article.

Magnetic moments

First magnetic susceptibility measurements on iron(III) dithiocarbamate complexes, leading to the discovery of the phenomenon of the spin-state equilibrium, were made by Cambi and Malatesta¹. Some 30 years later in 1964, White *et al.*³ confirmed the observations of Cambi and Malatesta and extended the measurements to solution. Since then several investigations^{4-8a-d} have been made in great detail, making elaborate measurements on temperature and pressure dependence and subjecting the data to rigorous theoretical treatment. Ewald *et al.*⁴ studied magnetic behavior of a series of eighteen iron(III) dithiocarbonates in the temperature range 80–40 K and evaluated crossover parameters for these complexes. De Lisle and Golding⁵ carried out a more refined treatment of the Ewald *et al.* data. They included configuration interaction with excited electronic states, spin-orbital interaction of the ${}^2T_{2g}$ with the ${}^4T_{1g}$ state and spin-orbital interaction of ${}^6A_{1g}$ with the ${}^4T_{1g}$ state. In the treatment, it was also necessary to include the partition coefficient ratio. Also, trigonal distortion of the ${}^2T_{2g}$ state was not explicitly treated. Figgis and Toogood⁶ reported the susceptibility of $\text{Fe}(\text{et}_2\text{-dte})_3$ from 4.2 to 100 K and fit their

data with the equations for a ${}^2T_{2g}$ level including spin-orbital interaction and trigonal distortion D. Hall and Hendrickson⁷ also carried out variable temperature magnetic susceptibility measurements on several intermediate spin $\text{Fe}(\text{dte})_3$ complexes down to 4.2 K and interpreted their data with the help of vibrational partition factor.

All the results reported so far are on the magnetic properties of the polycrystalline samples (and solutions in some cases), with emphasis on evolving theoretical models for interpretation of the data⁸. No work has so far been done on magnetic anisotropy of such systems.

Substituent effect :

Duffy and Uhrich⁹ proposed that the spin-crossover behavior of these compounds is influenced by the inductive effect of the substituents. In a more detailed study, Stahl and Ymen¹⁰ showed that there is no correlation between pK values of the parent secondary amines $\text{RR}'\text{NH}$ and the solid state magnetic moment values at room temperature. It is apparent that the substituents cause not only the electronic effect, but also other effects like steric etc., which may reflect into the magnetic property of the system.

Cooperative effect :

For iron(III) complexes of ligands other than dithiocarbamates it has been shown that the spin transitions are dependent upon the history of the sample^{10,11}. For example, a ferric compound, showing complete transition, exhibits incomplete transition on mechanically grinding. Spin transition in such compounds is described by cooperative phenomenon. But Stahl and Ymen¹⁰ studied effect of grinding on $\mu_{\text{eff}} - T$ curves of $\text{Fe}(\text{me}_2\text{-dte})_3$, $\text{Fe}(\text{et}_2\text{-dte})_3$, $\text{Fe}(\text{bu}_2\text{-dte})_3$ and $\text{Fe}(\text{bz}_2\text{-dte})_3$ to conclude that spin transitions of these complexes remain unaffected by grinding.

Solvent effect :

Crystallization of tris(dithiocarbamato)iron(III) from a

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solution often leads to the inclusion of the solvent molecules in the lattice. This solvent is incorporated in the lattice at the crystallographic position as verified by X-ray studies and is known to affect considerably the magnetic properties of the complexes¹²⁻¹⁸. It has been shown that the solvent molecules, which might interact with S atoms, shift the cross-over systems towards high-spin, while others have the opposite effect. Also, the solvents capable of hydrogen bonding such as H₂O, CHCl₃ and CH₂Cl₂ shift the system towards high-spin. Cuckauskas *et al.*¹⁷ carried out detailed magnetic susceptibility measurements on some benzene and dichloromethane solvated tris(dithiocarbamato)iron(III). The magnetic moments vs *T* curves are shown in Fig. 1. It is evi-

Fig. 1. Temperature dependence of effective magnetic moments of (a) Fe(pyrr-dtc)₃, (b) Fe(pyrr-dtc)₃·(C₆H₆)_{1/2}, (c) Fe(*n*-bu₂-dte)₃, (d) Fe(*n*-bu₂-dte)₃·(C₆H₆).

dent that the temperature-dependence of magnetic moment of the ferric complexes changes dramatically on solvation. In the C₆H₆ solvate, the spin-state equilibrium is displaced towards the low-spin side in the dichloromethane solvate. They suggested¹⁷ an equilibrium between a new intermediate quarter (*S* = 3/2) state and the high-spin sextet (*S* = 5/2) state. This was later refuted by Milliaris and Papaefthmiov¹⁸ who used Mössbauer data in conjugation with magnetic moment data to conclude that the spin state of iron(III) in these complexes involved only *S* = 1/2 and *S* = 5/2.

Pandeya *et al.*^{19a} reported the effect of water of crystallization on the spin state of tris(dihydroxyethyl dithiocarbamato)iron(III). The trihydrate shows magnetic moments of 2.13 B.M. at 15.3 K and 5.60 B.M. at 300 K, whereas the anhydrous analog shows magnetic moments of 2.00 B.M. at 15.0 K and 4.20 B.M. at 300 K (Fig. 2). Evidently the water of crystallization favors the low-spin state as also expected from the nature of the solvent.

Fig. 2. Temperature dependence of effective magnetic moments of Fe(dhe-dtc)₃ and Fe(dhe-dtc)₃·3H₂O.

Effect of doping :

Magnetic properties of iron(III) complexes are known²⁰ to undergo change on dilution with isostructural cobalt(III) and chromium(III) complexes. Hendrickson *et al.*²¹ carried out studies on effect of such doping on [Fe(3-OCH₃-Salen)₂]⁺ complexes. To our knowledge, there is only one report on the effect of such doping in the case of tris(dithiocarbamato)iron(III). Cuckauskas *et al.*¹⁷ studied magnetic properties of tris(1-pyrrolidine-carbodithionate)-iron(III) doped with the corresponding cobalt(III) complex. Doping with cobalt(III) increases the population of the low-spin state. This happens due to the occurrence of minor structural changes. Structure of tris(dithiocarbamato)iron(III) is modified with the shortening of Fe-S bond to approach the structure of tris(dithiocarbamato)cobalt(III) which has shorter metal-sulfur bond. Pandeya *et al.*^{19b} reported the effect of doping on the spin-state of the iron(III) complex of di(hydroxyethyl)dithiocarbamate. They studied the magnetic moments, Mössbauer and EPR properties of Fe_{1-x}Co_x(dhe-dtc)₃·3H₂O with *x* = 0.0, 0.2, 0.5 and 0.7. The complex with *x* = 0.0 is predominantly high-spin at room temperature and shows a gradual spin transition to low-spin state on decreasing the temperature. At and below 20 K, it is exclusively in low-spin state. Doping increases the population of the low-spin state and shifts the spin-crossover towards higher temperatures (Fig. 3). With the knowledge of the shift in the spin-state of Fe^{III}, it should be possible to design theoretically a doped system of desired magnetic moment.

Pressure dependence :

Ewald *et al.*⁴ measured the pressure-dependence of the

Fig. 3. Effect of doping on the spin-crossover phenomenon in $\text{Fe}(\text{dhe-dtc})_3$.

magnetic moment for several $\text{Fe}(\text{dtc})_3$ complexes in solution. For the ${}^2T_2 \rightleftharpoons {}^6A_1$ equilibrium, an equilibrium constant K may be defined as : $K = ({}^6A_1)/({}^2T_2)$. This equilibrium is related to ΔV , the difference in volume between the two states, by the thermodynamic relation,

$$[\partial \ln k_2 / \partial p]_T \Delta = -\Delta V / RT$$

In general, the value of ΔV is in order of $5\text{--}6 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ and can be attributed to the contraction in the FeS_6 core for 1 mole of the complex passing from the 6A_1 state to the 2T_2 state. This represents a change in the Fe-S bond length of about 0.1 \AA . Knowledge of physical properties under pressure is useful in context with the chemistry of the ocean bed.

Mössbauer spectra

Mössbauer spectroscopy is an important tool for the study of iron spin-crossover solids, since it can provide information about the relative amounts of high- and low-spin species, the microscopic environments of the ${}^{57}\text{Fe}$ nucleus, and the spin-state interconversion rates. Because of the intrinsic differences in the electronic properties of low- and high-spin states of iron(III), the two give distinctly different Mössbauer features. For a spin-crossover iron(III) system, the variable temperature Mössbauer results may conform to one of the following situations :

(i) If the electronic relaxation time between the high- and low-spin states is larger than the ${}^{57}\text{Fe}$ Mössbauer life-time ($1 \times 10^{-7} \text{ s}$), Mössbauer features corresponding to each spin-state will be observed separately. With decreasing temperature, the low-spin state feature will gain at the cost of the high-spin state feature.

(ii) If the electronic relaxation time between the two spin states is smaller than the ${}^{57}\text{Fe}$ Mössbauer life-time, population weighted average Mössbauer spectrum will be observed :

Mössbauer quadrupole splitting value will increase with decreasing temperature.

All iron(III)-dithiocarbamates (except our report^{19a}) show only one Mössbauer quadrupole doublet for which the quadrupole splitting value increases with decreasing temperature, in accordance to situation (ii). These observations have been interpreted in terms of average Mössbauer properties of the ${}^2T_{2g}$ and ${}^6A_{1g}$ states. Merrithew and Rasmussen²⁰ expressed doubts about the validity of such interpretation and suggested that the magnetic and Mössbauer properties of these complexes would better be explained in terms of spin-mixed states. Their suggestions, however, did not stand the test of time. It was demonstrated²¹ that the average Mössbauer spectrum results because of the relaxation between these states is just comparable to the life-time of the nuclear excited state ($\tau = 1.45 \times 10^{-7} \text{ s}$). By careful variation in the ligand structure in some systems other than iron(III)-dithiocarbamates, it has been shown that a system can exhibit averaged Mössbauer spectrum at one temperature and separate features for the two-spin states at another temperature²⁰. Tris-complex of iron(III) with dithiocarbamates (and monothiocarbamates and diselenocarbamates) were considered to be unique in the realm of the ferric spin crossover complexes in so far as they essentially interconvert the spin at a rate faster than can be detected by the Mössbauer technique. The reason for this relatively fast interconversion rate was considered to be the increased covalency and spin-orbit interactions present in the FeS_6 system. Also, no iron(III) complex of the ligands other than sulfur donors was known to show this property. But the scenario has now completely changed. Maeda *et al.*^{22a,b} reported several $\text{Fe}(\text{N}_4\text{O}_2)$ complexes which interconvert faster than detected by the Mössbauer technique. Several such reports follow²³⁻²⁹. Also, Pandeya *et al.*^{19a} reported two Mössbauer quadrupole doublets (at 78 K) for an iron(III)-dithiocarbamate complex, $\text{Fe}(\text{dhe-dtc})_3 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$, at liquid nitrogen temperature. These authors studied the Mössbauer spectra of $\text{Fe}(\text{dhe-dtc})_3 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and its anhydrous analog $\text{Fe}(\text{dhe-dtc})_3$ at room temperature (300 K) and also near liquid nitrogen temperature (78 K). While the anhydrous analog $\text{Fe}(\text{dhe-dtc})_3$ shows the common behaviour of iron(III)-dithiocarbamates, i.e. it shows population weighted average Mössbauer spectra with the quadrupole splitting value increasing at low temperatures (0.620 mm s^{-1} at 300 K and 0.33 at 78 K) (Fig. 4), the hydrated complex $\text{Fe}(\text{dhe-dtc})_3 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ shows two Mössbauer quadrupole doublets at liquid nitrogen temperature^{19a} (Fig. 5). But this remains to be the sole example of this kind so far. More and more data on such systems should be obtained to make the picture clearer.

Fig. 4. Mössbauer spectra of $\text{Fe}(\text{dhe-dtc})_3$ at 78 and 300 K.

Fig. 5. Mössbauer spectra of $\text{Fe}(\text{dhe-dtc})_3 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ at 78 and 300 K.

EPR spectra

EPR spectroscopy has the advantage of larger inverse time-scale (10^{10} s^{-1}) compared to the spin-crossover rates and provides a strong tool for studying the microscopic environment about the ferric ion during the spin-crossover transformation. Rickrada *et al.*³⁰ reported EPR spectrum of $\text{Fe}(\text{me}_2\text{-dte})_3$ at 4.2 K. The spectrum showed relatively isotropic signal with $g_1 = 2.111$, $g_2 = 2.076$, and $g_3 = 2.015$. Similar signal were later reported by Golding *et al.*³¹ for Mn^{III} -dithiocarbamate and they attributed the signals for both Fe^{III} and Mn^{III} complexes to a metal-sulfur complex with the unpaired electron on the sulfur. Flick and Gelerinter³² carried out variable temperature EPR studies on $\text{Fe}(\text{chx}_2\text{-dte})_3$ and observed signals attributable to the high-spin state and also those attributable to the low-spin state.

Hall and Hendrickson⁷ carried out detailed EPR investigations on several iron(III)-dithiocarbamates. For $\text{Fe}(\text{et}_2\text{-dte})_3$ in a CHCl_3 glass the X-band spectrum at 85 K shows

two signals at $g = 6.5$ and $g = 4.3$ and somewhat weaker signal at $g = 2$. At 12 K, the features are seen at $g = 4.36$, 3.26 and 1.83. The $g = 3.26$ and 1.83 signals arise from the ground state Kramers doublets of the 2T_2 state. For $\text{Fe}(\text{me}_2\text{-dte})_3$ doped into $\text{Co}(\text{me}_2\text{-dte})_3$ at 85 K a signal at $g = 4.71$ associated with 6A_1 population is observed. At 12 K, two new peaks at $g = 3.27$ and $g = 1.66$ are observed. The appearance of the distinct features for what appears to be molecules in the 6A_1 and 2T_2 levels is informative in so far as the rate of spin-flipping is concerned. Based on this fact the rate of spin-flipping for the $\text{Fe}(\text{dte})_3$ solid compounds is estimated between 10^7 and 10^{10} s^{-1} . The faster rate of spin-flipping in the $\text{Fe}(\text{dte})_3$ species compared to that for tris(monothio- β -diketonate)iron(III) compounds ($<10^7 \text{ s}^{-1}$) is mainly due to greater spin-orbital interaction. The spin-orbital interaction mixes 2T_2 state with 4T_1 state and 6A_1 state with 4T_1 state. Pandeya and Singh^{19c} carried out variable temperature (298–4.2 K) EPR spectral studies on $\text{Fe}(\text{dhe-dtc})_3 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Fig. 6). At and near liquid helium temperature where the complex is exclusively in low-spin state, a very broad signal showing g -tensor values of 2.0 and 3.2 is observed. The signal shows rapid loss in intensity with increase in temperature, possibly due to fast electronic relaxations. At room temperature, the spectrum shows a strong signal at $g = 2.0$ with a shoulder at $g = 2.5$ and weak signal at $g = 4.3$; all these features have been attributed to the high-spin state. The decrease in intensity of the $g = 2.0$ signal has been shown to correspond to the decrease in the population of the high spin state.

NMR spectra

Golding and Lehtonen³³ measured $E_{1/2}$ and the isotropic proton hyperfine interaction constant for a series of Fe^{III} -dte's and showed that there is a simple relationship between $E_{1/2}$ and the NCH_2 proton hyperfine interaction constant in the 6A_1 state (Table 1). It is also inferred that the redox process for these compounds takes place through the N atom.

Ganguli³⁴ investigated the high-spin–low-spin equilibrium in some tris(dithiocarbamate)iron(III) in different solvents using NMR and has interpreted the observations in terms of preferential solvation or second coordination sphere reorganization effects. These studies clearly demonstrate that neglect of pseudo-contact shift can lead to erroneous conclusions about the spin delocalization mechanisms. The spin delocalization in these systems is by direct π -delocalization along the alkyl chain. The A_s values of 2T_2 and 6A_1 states have the same sign. Surprisingly, in the NMR work on iron(III)-dithiocarbamates, ${}^1\text{H}$ has been the only probe nucleus, so far. Since, the technique has advanced immensely and powerful NMR spectrometers are now available, other

Fig. 6. EPR spectra of $\text{Fe}(\text{dhe-dtc})_3 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (polycrystalline) at (A) 300, (B) 9, (C) 4.2 K.

Table 1. Half-wave potentials and hyperfine interaction constants for some iron(III)-dithiocarbamates

Compd.	10^{-5} h.i.c.	$E_{1/2}$
	Hz	V
$\text{Fe}(\text{et}_2\text{-dte})_3$	4.52	-0.40
$\text{Fe}(\text{et,pr-dte})_3$	4.70	-0.41
$\text{Fe}(\text{bu,et-dte})_3$	4.68	-0.41
$\text{Fe}(\text{pr}_2\text{-dte})_3$	4.69	-0.42
$\text{Fe}(\text{bu,pr-dte})_3$	5.05	-0.42
$\text{Fe}(\text{bu}_2\text{-dte})_3$	4.58	-0.42
$\text{Fe}(\text{et,ph-dte})_3$	3.85	-0.35
$\text{Fe}(\text{morph-dte})_3$	3.12	-0.27
$\text{Fe}(\text{pip-dte})_3$	5.11	-0.42
$\text{Fe}(\text{pyrr-dte})_3$	2.65	-0.35
$\text{Fe}(\text{pyrrolin-dte})_3$	2.62	-0.29
$\text{Fe}(\text{azt-dte})_3$	2.76	-0.25

nuclei ${}^{13}\text{C}$, for example, should be explored.

Electronic spectra

A detailed study of the temperature and pressure dependence of some tris(dithiocarbamato)iron(III) compounds were made by Ewald *et al.*⁴. The spectra show definite trends as the population in the 6A_1 and 2T_2 varied either by the modification of the ligand or the variation of pressure and temperature. Nikolov³⁵ made detailed assignments of the various absorption bands taking the estimates of Ewald *et al.*⁴ for Δ and B . The pressure and temperature dependence of

the spectrum, obtained by Ewald *et al.*⁴ supports the assignments proposed in this table. Butcher *et al.*³⁶ observed that in tris(*N,N*-di-*n*-propyldithiocarbamato)iron(III) weak absorption bands at 19000 cm^{-1} grows slightly in prominence on increasing the pressure from 1 to 6000 atmosphere. This is in agreement with the assignment of Ewald *et al.*⁴ as ${}^2T_2 \rightarrow {}^2T_1, {}^2A$ and with the expectation that increased pressure favours the low spin (2T_2) ground state.

Infrared spectra

Tris(dithiocarbamato)iron(III) systems involving in spin-crossover should have two Fe-S stretching frequency bands for the two spin states^{8,37-46}. Tris(*N*-ethyl-*N*-phenyldithiocarbamato)iron(III)⁴ has two bands in the iron-sulfur region, suggestive of two species, and the intensity ratio changes with pressure. If pressure-broadening is allowed for, the higher energy band increases while the lower energy one decreases. This indicates increasing concentration of the species with stronger Fe-S bands (low-spin) at the expense of that with the weaker bond (high-spin).

Hall and Hendrickson⁷ carried out variable temperature IR investigations on $\text{Fe}(\text{et}_2\text{-dte})_3$ and $\text{Fe}(\text{n-pr}_2\text{-dte})_3$. They assigned a band system at $\sim 300\text{ cm}^{-1}$ to the high-spin Fe-S and another band system at $302\text{--}350\text{ cm}^{-1}$ to the low-spin one. With decreasing temperature, the low-spin Fe-S band system gains intensity at the cost of high-spin Fe-S band system. Appearance of distinct bands reflecting the thermal population in the two spin-states suggests that the spin-flip-

ping rate is less than the vibrational time scale ($\leq 10^{13} \text{ s}^{-1}$). The observation that the high spin Fe-S is at higher energy than the low-spin Fe-S, is peculiar and has been explained in terms of the strong vibronic nature of these complexes. Sorai⁴⁶ studied in detail the IR spectra and spin equilibrium between the 6A_1 and 2T_1 states in tris(*N,N*-diethyldithiocarbamato)iron(III) (Fig. 7).

Fig. 7. Comparison of the peak areas of the characteristic IR bands with the high-spin content as a function of temperature.

Crystal structure

Leipoldt and Coppens⁴⁷ studied correlations between structure and temperature dependent magnetic behavior of $\text{Fe}(\text{et}_2\text{-dte})_3$. The compound is predominantly in the high-spin state at room temperature with a magnetic moment of 4.3 B.M. and predominantly in the low-spin state at 79 K with a magnetic moment of 2.2 B.M.⁴. The crystal structure of the complex has been determined from three-dimensional counter data at 297 and at 79 K to correlate the temperature-dependence of its magnetic moment (4.3 and 2.2 B.M. at the two temperatures, respectively) with structural changes. The space group of the crystal changes on cooling from $p2_1 / C$ to $C2 / n$. Lattice constants are $a = 14.29$ (1), $b = 10.37$ (1), $c = 17.87$ (1) Å, $\beta = 116.6$ (1) at 297 K and $a = 13.96$ (1), $b = 10.24$ (1), $c = 17.71$ (1) Å, $\beta = 116.5$ (1) at 79 K, $Z = 4$ at both temperatures. At room temperature, the iron atoms are located on a pseudo-two-fold axis, which becomes a true two-fold axis in the low temperature structure. The change in space group is accompanied by a contraction of the Fe-S distances of 0.05 Å and a small but significant decrease in distortion from octahedral symmetry of the FeS_6 group. Slight differences in the geometry of the ligand at the two temperatures are compatible with a mechanism by which the effect of the substituent on the crystal field is transmitted through the conjugated system of the ligand. By analysis of the temperature parameters at room

temperature these authors showed that the diffraction data can not distinguish between a mixed spin-state and the existence of a mixture of two different spin-states as an explanation for the variability of the magnetic moment. Albertsson and Oskarsson⁴⁸ carried out X-ray crystal structure determination on tris[*N,N*-bis(2-hydroxyethyl)dithiocarbamato]iron(III) at 150 and 295 K. The main structural difference at the two temperatures is a decrease of the average Fe-S distance from 2.390(3) Å at 295 K to 2.331(3) Å at 150 K. This is accompanied by a decrease in the magnetic moment from $\mu_{\text{eff}} = 4.20$ to 2.40.

Stahl and Ymen¹⁰ studied in detail the linear correlation among 10 mean geometric parameters and magnetic moments using data for several $\text{Fe}(\text{dte})_3$ complexes⁴⁷⁻⁵⁵. Since the spin state is dependent on the ligand field strength, a strong correlation is observed between parameters of the FeS_6 core and μ_{eff} . Within the ligands, the only parameters significantly correlated to μ_{eff} are the S-C-S and C-N-C angles. Consequently, also S-C-S and C-N-S are correlated to each other. According to Stahl and Ymen¹⁰, the correlation can be deduced from steric interference within the ligands. Steric crowding between the substituents is propagated to the S-atoms through a variable number of C-H...S interactions. This steric interference is balanced by an increased repulsion between the S-atoms. These authors concluded that the weak steric interference (e.g. in tetramethylene dte) results in ligand bites producing a weak ligand field⁵⁶⁻⁵⁸ and Fe^{III} remains high-spin. When the steric interference is strong (e.g. in diisopropyl or other di-secondary alkyl dte's) the resulting smaller ligand bite produces a strong ligand field and Fe^{III} becomes low-spin. Also, when the steric interference is intermediate (e.g. in dimethyl, diethyl or other di-primary alkyl dte's) the ligand bite and ligand field are intermediate and the corresponding iron(III) complex exhibits spin-crossover behavior. This model also explains the high-spin behavior when the substituents are methyl and methoxy groups^{8a,b}.

Kinetics and mechanism of spin-crossover

In the last few years attention has been directed to understanding the kinetics and mechanism of spin-crossover transformation. A given complex inter-converts between low-spin and high-spin electronic states in what amounts to an intramolecular electron transfer reaction. In the solution state, there is a dynamic equilibrium present with a Boltzmann distribution of spin-crossover complexes in low-spin ground state and high-spin excited state. Spin-crossover interconversion for complexes in solutions has been measured by relaxation techniques⁵⁹⁻⁶⁸ and the theory of radiationless non-adiabatic multiphonon processes has been

applied (Buhks *et al.*⁶⁹) to estimate the spin-state interconversion. Spin-crossover transformations in solid state, however, come in a variety of types. Some are essentially discontinuous, i.e. the sample changes between the high-spin excited state and low-spin ground state within a few degrees. These transformations are first order phase transitions⁴⁶. Haddad *et al.*^{12,24,70} used the nucleation and growth mechanism of phase transition in solids⁷¹ to account for the degree of sharpness in the transition. This mechanism also accounts for the incomplete transitions and the sensitivity of spin-crossover systems to solvation and sample preparation. Another kind of spin-crossover transition in the solid state is gradual. Fe(dtc)₃ crossover system falls in this category. In general, little is known, as yet, of the nature and mechanism of gradual transformations. It is suggested that the two spin isomers in such system form a solid solution within the same lattice. The transformation does not involve a crystallographic phase change and, therefore, develops over a wide range of temperature.

Fe(dtc)₃ and also Fe(monothiocarbamate)₃⁷² and Fe(diselenocarbamate)₃⁷³ are unique spin-crossover systems¹² in so far as they flip spin at a very fast rate, faster than detectable by the ⁵⁷Fe Mössbauer technique ($\sim 10^7$ s⁻¹). The upper limit for the spin flipping rates have been established by EPR data as less than $\sim 10^7$ s⁻¹. Studies on spin-crossover systems have revealed that the spin-flipping rates can be altered by structural manipulations²¹⁻²⁹. Pandeya *et al.*^{19a} reported an iron(III)-dithiocarbamate complex, Fe(dhe-dtc)₃·3H₂O, whose spin flipping rate has been detected by the Mössbauer technique at liquid nitrogen temperature. In this work the most important observation is that the trihydrate flips spin at a rate detectable by Mössbauer spectroscopy at least at liquid nitrogen temperature, but the anhydrous analog, Fe(dhe-dtc)₃, flips spin at much faster rate like other Fe(dtc)₃ complexes, so that the two spin states are not detected by the Mössbauer spectroscopy.

Further scope

It has recently been realized that the spin-crossover compounds could be used as active elements in memory devices. In fact, spin-crossover phenomenon provides the most spectacular example of molecular bistability, a property that makes a molecule or a molecular assembly suitable for information processing. This area of research has, therefore, attained immense importance in the field of material science. Several research papers have appeared⁷⁴⁻⁸⁵ during last decade on the attempts to find application of iron(II) spin crossover systems as memory devices. Similar research on iron(III) spin crossover systems is yet to begin.

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